

HISTORY OF THE ORIGIN AND PROSPECTS OF FOOTBALL WITHIN SPORTS, FOOTBALL.

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Annotation: Football (English : football ; foot — "foot", ball — "ball") is a sports game. The goal of the game is to get the ball into the opponent's goal . This is attempted by the goalkeeper of each team , who is allowed to touch the ball with his hand inside the penalty area near his own goal. All other players, as well as the goalkeeper who goes outside his own penalty area, are not given this right. During the fight for the ball, it is forbidden to use force such as knocking down, hitting the opponent. If a player is in a position to hit the ball with any part of his body (usually his feet) other than his hands, the player is considered in possession of the ball. Football is usually played on a rectangular field .

Key word: For the ball, 2 sections of 45 minutes, Football Brazil , Germany , Italy , Argentina , Farg'ana , Samarkand , Tashkent , Andijan . [1-5]

INTRODUCTION. Each team consists of 11 players (10 players and one goalkeeper). An individual soccer game is called a match, and consists of 45 - minute halves each . Between the first and second halves, the teams change places. There are also types of football that may have fewer players - including beach football (played on sand), mini football (played in a specially covered hall), neighborhood football (played on any field with any number of players). The size of the gates is proportional to the size of the field. Football is played as a team with a ball on a special field (90-120 x 45-90) with two goals (7.32 x 2.44 m). The weight of the soccer ball is 410-450 g, the length of the circle diameter is 68-70 cm, the main time of the game is 90 minutes (2 sections of 45 minutes, a break of 12-15 minutes). Football-like games Egypt BC and was known in Eastern countries, and then moved

to Europe. In 1848 in Great Britain Cambridge University teachers developed the first modern football rules . [5-8] In 1857, the first football club was founded in the city of Sheffield in this country. In 1863, the English Football Association was established and football rules were approved. Europe at the end of the 18th century - at the beginning of the 19th century and Football associations were also established in South American countries. In 1896, football was included in the program of the Olympic Games. In 1904, the international football federation - FIFA was established. Football is widely developed in countries such as Brazil , Germany , Italy , Argentina , Great Britain. From the beginning of the 20th century, matches were played in Uzbekistan based on modern football rules . [13-17-22] In 1912, the first football team was formed in Kok . Later, football teams appeared in the cities of Farg'ana , Samarkand , Tashkent , Andijan , and Namangan . Since the 20s of the 20th century, competitions of various categories (Uzbekistan championship since 1937) have been regularly held in our country. In 1956, the establishment of the "Pakhtakor" team in Tashkent and the construction of the stadium of the same name gave impetus to the development of football in the republic. From the 80s of the 20th century, a new generation of football players was brought up in Uzbekistan. Soccer ball soccer ball is a ball . According to football rules, the circumference of the ball should be 68-70 cm, the mass should be 410-450 g, the internal air pressure should be 55-80 kPa , and it should be covered with leather or similar material.

Relevance of the topic: The standardization of soccer balls began in 1863 , when the rules for the shape of the balls were introduced. 1872 - year this to the rules changes entered . Current balls are 32-sided spherical icosahedrons , 12 of which are regular pentagons and 20 regular hexagons . Icosahedron and soccer ball Soccer balls were originally of one color: brown, white. In the 1960s, balls were painted black-and-white for broadcasts of football matches on black-and-white television . With the advent of color television, this practice became unnecessary, and now the balls are painted in different colors. Football The area is rectangular and covered with natural

grass. The football field should also be equipped with a number of additional equipment . That is, gates, nets, flags must meet the specified requirements.

The length of a football field	---	90-120 meters
The width of the football field	---	45-90 meters
Penalty area	---	16.5 meters by 40.32 meters
Goalkeeper area	---	18.32 meters by 5.5 meters
Lines on the field	---	12 cm
Corner kick	---	1 m ² at 90 degrees
The center of the field is the radius of the circle	---	9.15 meters
The weight of the soccer ball	---	410-450 grams
Circling the soccer ball	---	68-71 cm
Air pressure on a soccer ball	---	0.6-1.1

General description of football game rules. The rules of the football game mean all the requirements for the organization and conduct of the game. In addition, restrictions, bans and other situations on the football playing field, football balls, the number and clothing of players, referees' activities, game time and all situations in the game are governed by the requirements established in the rules of the football game. .

	1- Playground
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	2nd ball
	3-Number of players
	4- players' clothes
	5- Chief referee
	6- Chief referee assistants
	7-Time of the game
	8- start and continuation of the game
	9- In the game and in situations outside the game
	10- determining whether the ball is in the net
	11-"Offside" state
	12- Violation of rules and illegal behavior
	13th penalty and free kick
	14-11 meter free kick
	15- Bringing the ball into play from the sideline
	16- Putting the ball into the game with a free kick from the side of the goal
	17th corner balls

The Football Federation of Uzbekistan, founded in 1959, was re-registered in 1992 (then in 2001). Since 1992, the national football championship and cup of Uzbekistan, competitions of various categories have been held, the participation of football teams in international meetings is ensured. [1-9] Theoretical part: Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers "On measures to further develop football in the Republic of Uzbekistan" (March 18, 1993) and "On measures to fundamentally

improve the organizational foundations and principles of football development in Uzbekistan" (January 17, 1996) his decisions laid the foundation for success in football. The Neftchi club of Fergana reached the finals of the CIS Cup (1994), the Pakhtakor club played in the semi-finals of the Asian Champions League (2003, 2004), the country's youth national team participated in the finals of the World Championship (2003), the national team of Uzbekistan participated in the Asian Games (1994) and won the Africa-Asian Games (2003). Currently, there are 36 (higher and first league) professional clubs in Uzbekistan (2004). [12-18] 196 teams in the 2nd league are participating in the national championship to achieve such a status. 18 football boarding schools and colleges operate under football clubs, and more than 2,000 students study in them. Also, the work of sports schools for children and teenagers specializing in football has improved. Football took place in the Universiade, "Barkamol Avlod " and "Umid Nihollar" competitions. 13,840 players from 692 teams participated in the "Football Bud" competitions held in the republic among children and teenagers, and 300,700 players participated in the "Future of our Football" competitions from 15,035 teams (2004). The teams of "Andijanka" of Andijan, "Gulbahor" of Namangan, "Sevinch" of Karshi are leading in the championship and cup competitions of Uzbekistan held among women . Competitions are also regularly organized among veteran players. "Matonat " team of Tashkent (now "Baynalmilal") won the world cup among players with limited physical abilities (1991). Currently, the republic has 362 stadiums, 7,113 football fields, 460,658 people (4,642 of whom are women) play football, and 1,916 coaches (2004). Specialized newspapers such as "Uzbekistan football " (Tashkent), "FutbolExpress" (Andijan), "Asr football" (Namangan), "Inter football" (Kosonsoy), "Boxing plus football" (Tashkent) are published. S. Arutyunov, Ye. Valitsky, A. Keller, M. Akbarov, R. Akramov, Yu. Coaches like Sarkisyan, M. Rahimov are of great service to the development of Uzbek football. I. Kutsillo managed official prestigious international competitions. of football -like games goes back to BC.

Today's modern football is based on the rules prepared by the Football Association, which was founded in England in 1863

Discussion section: History of origin ed edit the source According to FIFA , the first game that is similar to soccer and has scientific evidence is juju, a sport played for military training in China between 300 and 200 BC. The goal of this game is to roll a ball of leather filled with wool, fixed by two bamboo canes, into a castle 30-40 cm high; the ball could be touched by any part of the body except the hands and arms. A few centuries later, a game called kemari appeared in Japan , which also has traces of juju, dating back to 644 AD. Unlike Cuju, the non-competitive game of kemara was based on players kicking the ball around a circular field and passing the ball to each other without dropping the ball. The first game similar to soccer in Europe was a game called episkyros, played in Ancient Greece . In a free contact game with every part of the body, the players are divided into two teams and each team tries to get the ball over the line at the end of the opposing team's field by passing or shooting. A similar game was played later in the Roman Empire The modern rules of football, called harpastum, are based on forms of football played with different rules in private schools in England in the mid-19th century. The Cambridge Rules, created with the participation of representatives of Eton , Harrow , Rugby , Winchester and Shrewsbury educational institutions, play a very effective role in the development of football and similar sports. Although some games were played using these rules, they were not adopted by the senior team. In the 1850s, various clubs in English-speaking countries broke away from their schools or universities and began to operate as independent organizations. Some of them created their own rules and started playing football according to these rules. Founded in 1857 by former students, Sheffield Football Club took the initiative to form the Sheffield Football Association in 1867 . John Charles Thring, a student at Uppingham School , also developed some rules in 1862. [11-19]

CONCLUSION: The first comprehensive rules for football were prepared between October and November of that year, as a result of five meetings held by the

Football Association ("The Football Association", abbreviated "FA"), which was established after the meeting held in October . After the establishment of the Football Association, football began to be spread around the world by the British. The first football match in South America was played by British workers in Argentina in 1867 . In the same year, Buenos Aires Football Club, the first football club in South America, was founded in Buenos Aires. In 1891, together with the national league established in Argentina, the first football tournament was organized on the continent. The English living in South Africa started the first football movement in the country in 1869, and the first football tournament was held in the country in 1884. In 1884, the first football competition organized by the American Football Association will be held. The first known records of soccer being played in Japan date back to the 1870s, when British sailors played soccer in Yokohama . After the spread of football, the International Football Association Board (IFAB for short) was established in Manchester in 1886 after a meeting of the Football Association of Scotland, Football Association of Wales and Football Association of Ireland. [29-32] Federation of International Football Associations (FIFA for short) is the highest governing body of football in the international arena, founded in 1904 in Paris and declared to follow the rules set by the Football Association. In 1913, representatives of FIFA also began to send representatives to IFAB. The process of professionalization in football developed rapidly in different parts of the world in 1920-1930. In the 20th century, football, played by more than 250 million players in more than 200 countries, becomes the most popular sport in the world. According to a report published by FIFA in May 2007, more than 270 million people around the world play football. According to this report, there are more than 301 thousand football clubs, more than 1752 million football teams, more than 840 thousand football referees and more than 113 thousand professional players in the world.

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